

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Qoraqo'ziyeva Diyora

THE CONCEPT OF "WOLF" IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGE

WEBSITE: WWW.REANDPUB.UZ

EMAIL: INFO@REANDPUB.UZ

2023/APREL

